

Effects of Jig-Saw (III) Cooperative Learning strategy on Achievement and Retention in Algebra among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Enrich Jig-saw (III) Cooperative Strategy on achievement and retention in Algebra among Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna State. The population of the study consists of 1,061 (644 Males and 471 Females) Senior Secondary class II (SSII) Students in government secondary schools during the 2020/2021 academic session in Zaria, Kaduna State. A sample of 70 students (59 male and 11 female) were randomly selected using two intact classes. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest, post -test and post post-test design was employed. The two groups were pretested to determine their equivalence, the experimental group was exposed to Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Strategy while the control group were taught same concept using lecture method. An Algebra Performance Test (APT) was used to collect data with reliability co-efficient of 0.78 achieved using cronbach alpha reliability test. The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 significant level using t-test inferential statistics. The results showed that the experimental group exposed to Enrich Jig-saw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy achieved significantly higher results and retained better when taught the same concepts than their counterparts exposed to lecture method. It was recommended that Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy should be employed as a teaching strategy by Mathematics teachers in teaching Algebra in senior secondary schools in Zaria and Kaduna Sate as a whole.

Keyword: Jigsaw III Cooperative learning Strategy, Algebra, Achievement, Retention.

Introduction

Mathematics in general is linked with the development of any nation in the world, mathematics as a discipline opens and shuts doors for men and women than any other content area we have got. Whether it is in science, engineering, or technology, it is tremendously important that a person be well armed with mathematics if they are to have options in their lives (Thompson,2003). Mathematics is intimately involved in every moment of everyone's life. Right from human existence on this earth, it has been a faithful companion. The role played by mathematics in the day-to-day activities of human endeavors is suggestive of the fact that mathematics is needed by all, not only for scientific and technological development, but for all forms of development. Mathematics is one of the core subjects to be offered to all students up to the tertiary levels of education (Salau, 2005). This compulsory nature of mathematics carries with it the assumption that the knowledge of the subject is essential for all members of society.

A variety of teaching strategies have been advocated for use in science and mathematics classrooms ranging from teacher-centered approach to more students-centered ones. One of such methods according to Oloruko-oba, (2001) is cooperative learning. Cooperative learning is a strategy in which students create, analyze, and apply concepts. Here, students learn lifelong concepts that will be useful both inside and outside the school. They work as a team, combining their knowledge and social skills. Students are often placed in heterogeneous groups and asked to accomplish a common goal. Each team member is assigned part of the content to be learnt and is not only responsible for their learning, but the other group members' learning as well. Students work until each group member successfully understands all concepts and then the assignment is completed (Timayi, Bolaji, & Kajuru, 2015). There are several models of Cooperative Learning Strategies one of which is Jig-saw Cooperative Learning model.

Jigsaw is a cooperative learning strategy that was developed by Elliot Aronson and his colleagues in 1978. The jigsaw technique was created with the goals of reducing conflict, enhancing positive educational outcomes and to help students realize they are essential components of a whole and encourages cooperation in a learning environment. There are currently six types of Jigsaw cooperative learning strategies available for teachers to use in the classroom. Algebra is that branch of mathematics that deals with the study of rules of operations and things, which can be constructed from them including terms, polynomials, equations and algebraic structure (Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia 2010). Hence, good skills and competencies in Algebra is a great asset to any secondary school student because it is a tool for developing critical and logical thinking that can facilitate

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the learning of other branches of mathematics and even other science subjects. Oluremi and Ajao (2012) reported that secondary school students tend to fear and hate Algebraic concepts to the extent that they avoid Algebraic questions in both internal and external examinations. This consequently affects students' academic achievement in mathematics negatively.

Academic achievement refers to student's success in meeting short- or long-term goals in education. Sani (2007) defines academic achievement as an accomplishment or proficiency of performance in each skill or body of knowledge. Adediwura and Tayo (2007), viewed academic performance as the knowledge attained or skills developed in school subject designed by test and examination scores, or marks assigned by the subject teachers. According to Nwagbo (2013), academic achievement can be defined as performance of students in schools. Academic achievement could be getting a high grade or a high-Grade Point Average (GPA).

Retention is the act of keeping something in one's memory or the ability to remember or recollect a body of knowledge after passing through instruction. In other words, retention refers to what is learned minus what has been forgotten (Mang and Mankilik, 2001). Retention is the ability of a learner to recall, remember and recollect a body of Knowledge after passing through instruction. For students' retention, Omar, (2012) observed that students' experience is a significant factor in retention and that the strategies of improving retention rate can be adopted by the teacher.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate effects of Enrich Jig-saw (III) Cooperative Strategy on achievement and retention in Algebra among senior secondary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the effects of Enrich Jig-saw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy (EJ3CLS) on Students' Academic Achievement in Algebra in Senior Secondary Schools.
2. Determine the retention ability of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS with those taught using Lecture Method.

Research Questions

The study sought answers to the following research questions.

1. Is there any difference in mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School students taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Strategy and those taught using Lecture Method?
2. Is there any difference in retention ability of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS and those taught using Lecture Method?

Null hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS and those taught using Lecture Method.
2. There is no significant difference between mean retention ability of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS and those taught using Lecture Method.

Methodology

The design for this study is a quasi-experimental research design. The experimental group (EG) was exposed Algebra concepts using EJ3CLS while control group (CG) was exposed to Algebra concepts using lecture method. The sample selected was pre-tested to ensure that the two groups are not significantly different. A post- test was administered to determine the difference in students' academic achievement among the groups. A post-post-test was equally administered to both experimental and control group to ascertain difference in students' retention ability in Algebraic concepts. The population of this study comprised of all government secondary schools' senior class (SS II) students offering mathematics in Zaria, Kaduna Sate. There are eleven government secondary schools in Zaria metropolis with a total of 1061 SS II students. 644 students were males while 417 students were females. Two schools were randomly selected, that is G.S.S. Jama'a and G.S.S. Kaura and used as sample with an enrolment of 70 students were subjected to pretest as the sample of the study. The two sample schools were assigned as experimental group consisting of 36 students and the other school as control group (CG) having 34 students. In both experimental and control groups, 59 students were male, and 11 students were female. An instrument called Algebra Performance Test (APT) was used to collect data. The APT was constructed by the researcher. It was made up of 30 multiple choice items on algebra. Concept. The instrument was used for both posttest and post-posttest. The APT was validated by Senior Lecturers in Science Education Department Federal University, Gusau. This was to determine the appropriateness of the test item, language used and content validity. The APT was pilot tested at GSS Gyalesu. The results were used to determine the reliability co-efficient which was found to be 0.78 using Cronbach alpha reliability test.

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Results

Research Question 1

Is there any difference in mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School students taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Strategy and those taught using Lecture Method?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of mean scores of pre-tests and post-test scores

Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean Diff.
Pre- Test	36	67.9	8.63	24.7
Post-Test	34	43.2	3.95	

Source: field work (2023)

Table 1 above showed that there is difference in the mean scores of pre-test and post-test scores of students taught algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) cooperative strategy. From the table, pre-test group has a mean score of 67.9 with standard deviation of 8.63 as against post-test group with a mean score of 43.2 and standard deviation of 3.95

Research Question 2

Is there any difference in retention ability of students taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative strategy and those taught using Lecture Method?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of mean scores of post-tests and post post-test scores

Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean Diff.
Post-Test	36	78.5	7.93	32.7
Post Post-Test	34	45.8	3.43	

Source: field work (2023)

Table 2 above showed that there is difference in retention ability of students taught algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) cooperative strategy. From the table, post-test scores have a mean score of 78.5 with a standard deviation of 7.93 against post post-test scores with a mean score of 45.8 and standard deviation of 3.43

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of students taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Strategy and those taught using Lecture Method.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of mean Scores of Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Post-test scores	SD	SE	t-cal	t-crit	Df	p-value
Experimental	34	50.76	17.70	3.04	4.59	2.01	68	0.001
Control	36	46.17	17.22	2.87				

Source: field work (2023)

From Table 3, the p-value of 0.001 is less than the critical p-value of 0.05 with df = 68. This means that there is a significant difference between mean scores of experimental group and control group in favor of the experimental group. Thus, hypothesis one is rejected. This implies that the experimental group taught Algebra concepts using Enriched Jig-saw Cooperative Strategy performed significantly higher than those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significance difference in mean retention ability of students taught Algebra using EJ3CLS and those taught using Lecture Method.

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Table 4: t-test Analysis of Post-posttest Mean Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Post Post-test	SD	SE	t-cal	t-crit	Df	p-value
Exp.	34	51.06	20.91	3.59	4.75	2.01	68	0.001
Control	36	46.31	17.84	2.89				

Source: field work (2023)

From Table 4, p – value of 0.001 less is than the critical P-value of 0.05 with df = 68. This means that there is a significant difference between the post post-test means score of the experimental and control groups in favor of the experimental group. Thus, hypothesis two is rejected. This implies that the experimental group taught Algebra concepts using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy retained the learned concepts better than the control group taught same concepts using lecture method. So, the null hypothesis which says there is no significant difference is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The results obtained from the analysis of data, in Table 3 shows that students in the experimental group (EG) taught Algebra using Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy (EJ3CLS) achieved significantly higher than their counterparts in the control group (CG) taught same concepts using lecture method. The significant difference in the academic achievement in favor of the experimental group suggests a greater strength and effectiveness of EJ3CLS over the lecture method. This finding is in conformity with those of Naomi (2013), & Timay, etal (2015) which showed that Enrich Jigsaw Cooperative Learning Strategy is superior and more effective in improving students’ academic performance than the traditional lecture method.

The post-post test results Table 4 showed that the experimental group exposed to Algebra concepts using EJ3CLS had significantly higher retentive ability than those exposed to lecture method. Therefore, the statistically significant difference between the two mean scores suggests that the EJ3CLS is more effective in enhancing students’ retention ability. The results agrees with the earlier findings of Jansoon; Somsook and Coll, (2008); Zakari & Iksan, (2007) and Timayi, etal (2015) each of them reported that Jigsaw Cooperative Learning Strategy on the academic achievement and retention of student in science and Mathematics and revealed that EJ3CLS enhances the retention ability of students.

Conclusion

This study confirmed the superiority of Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy (EJ3CLS) over the lecture method in the teaching of Algebra. Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative strategy (EJ3CLS) improves achievement and retention during teaching and learning of algebra concept.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Kaduna State Ministry of Education Science and Technology should organize training programs for mathematics teachers in a form of seminars, workshops, and conferences on how to effectively use Enrich Jigsaw (III) Cooperative Learning Strategy in the teaching of Algebra concepts in Senior Secondary Schools.
2. Algebra should be given more teaching time by mathematics teachers because of its abstract nature for students to understand its concepts better.

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